

Intelligent Grid Optimization for Cooperative Energy Systems

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Abstract—SEAS Shared Intelligence (SEAS SI) is a platform for algorithms sharing and execution developed under the scope of Smart Energy Aware Systems (SEAS) project to promote the intelligent management of smart grids and microgrids, by means of the shared usage of algorithms and tools, while ensuring code and intellectual protection. In this paper the platform goals and architecture are described, focusing on the recent achievement regarding the connection of distinct algorithms, which enables the execution of dynamic simulations using sequences of algorithms from distinct sources. A case study based on several SEAS SI available algorithms is presented with the objective of showing the advantages of the SEAS SI capability of supporting simulations based on sequences of algorithms. Namely, electricity market bid values are calculated by a metalearner, which is fed by market price forecasts using different methods, and by their respective forecasting errors. A case study presents some results to validate the presented work, through the simulation of the MIBEL electricity market using MASCEM (Multi-Agent Simulator of Competitive Electricity Markets).

Forecasting; Metalearning; Shared Intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

Distributed generation was a driver for the power and energy systems complete rethinking of traditional practices [1]. A lot of challenges remain: How to accommodate in an efficient and secure way the intensive use of renewable based and distributed generation together with demand flexibility? How to face a high penetration of electric vehicles (EVs)? How to assure and obtain knowledge from real-time monitoring? How to communicate and assure interoperability between different technologies and players? To address these challenges cross industry and cross domain cooperation is required [2].

Smart Energy Aware Systems (SEAS) is a project under the ITEA initiative that aims at enabling interactions for all market players in real time, for consumption and production energy systems, automation and ICT in order to optimize

global energy consumption. Project most ambitious goal is to define a common language and intelligence to all types of energy aware technologies, consumers and producers [3].

This paper focuses on the common intelligence and how it is being achieved under the SEAS's vision, by means of different algorithms, from different partners, written and executed in different languages and IDEs, with complementary or competitive approaches, available through a Shared Intelligence platform (SI). The currently available algorithms enable the integration of partner's approaches to be tested in case studies, and afterwards implemented in project pilots. The main focus of this paper is put on the ability of SEAS SI in supporting the execution of multiple algorithms sequentially. The platform thus allows defining simulations composed by sequences of algorithms and specifying connections between outputs and inputs of different algorithms (from different sources and locations) in a way that the results of algorithms can be directly used by others, sequentially or in parallel.

This paper includes a case study that considers the execution of two forecasting algorithms, namely an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) [4] and a Support Vector Machine Regression (SVM) [5], to predict electricity market prices. The results of these algorithms are used by a forecasting evaluation method – the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), to assess the quality of the forecasts. Finally, the forecasted market prices and the associated error values are used as inputs for a metalearner algorithm [6] which generates the bids for one-day participation in the electricity market, by combining the prices suggested by the different forecasts, and associating confidence weights based on their forecasting error for the different periods of the day. Real data from the Iberian Electricity Market – MIBEL [7], is used for this case study. The full version of the paper will include the validation of the results through the simulation of the MIBEL electricity market using MASCEM [8].

After this introductory section, section II described the SEAS – SI platform and section III provides an overview of the considered algorithms for the collaborative sequential simulation. In Section IV the case study shows how complementary intelligence can be achieved, focusing on the electricity market participation scenario using the SEAS SI available algorithms, and validated using a simulation of MIBEL in MASCEM. The conclusions are fully drawn in section V.

II. SHARED INTELLIGENCE PLATFORM

SEAS is an Eureka project, under the cluster ITEA, with nr. 12004, coordinated by ENGIE and involving 36 partners, with a total of 6 academic/research and 30 industrial ones, from 7 different countries. SEAS project addresses the problem of inefficient and unsustainable energy consumption, which is due to a lack of insufficient means to control, monitor, estimate and adapt energy usage of systems versus the dynamic usage situations and circumstances influencing the energy usage.

SEAS Shared Intelligence (SEAS SI) was developed under SEAS project with the goal of providing a unique platform for algorithms sharing between partners [9]. SEAS SI allows the execution of algorithms in a standalone, sequential or complementary way. Algorithms confidentiality is provided by means of a distributed system where algorithms are accessible to all the partners while keeping them running in its owner server. This methodology enables the code protection and intellectual protection while allowing the share of knowledge and intelligence between partners.

A. Shared Intelligence

The main goal of SEAS SI is the sharing of algorithms between partners without compromising the confidentiality of the algorithm. The sharing of intelligence is a very important topic in our days and enables the growth of science contributions. In big projects, like SEAS, the sharing of intelligence can be difficult to manage between partners. The creation of a unified and common platform enables and promotes these sharing while dealing with restrictions of confidentiality and protection.

Algorithms are executed in the Web Service side and use Excel files for data input and output, enabling the use of SEAS SI in the ordinary computer without the need of additional software installation, even if using different programming languages and environments. The Web Services currently used in SEAS SI were developed in WFC framework, however SEAS SI supports communication by web services developed within other frameworks. The use of SEAS SI enables the sharing of intelligence between SEAS partners and enables the

execution of algorithms sequences, when the output of an algorithm is automatically used as input for another one.

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Fig. 1. Screenshot of SEAS SI: ANN algorithm

For each algorithm available in SEAS SI, input and output variables, regarding the name, description and variable type are described, a downloadable file with detailed algorithms description and parameters is also available.

At this moment, algorithms are executed in four different programming languages: C#, MATLAB, TOMLAB and R. Additional programming languages can be used while sharing new algorithms. The number of different programming languages used by the developers does not compromise the platform availability or efficiency.

B. Architecture

The architecture and functionalities of SEAS SI can be seen in Figure 2. On the top of the figure platform characteristics are presented. SEAS SI is based on a Web Service Aggregator that combines all the Web Services distributed by the partners and present them as a unique and unified platform. SEAS SI is available as a website with an authentication service, to restrict algorithms availability only for SEAS partners [9].

Algorithms execution is available through online and offline modes. These modes are automatically chosen according to the execution time of each algorithm. For example, if an algorithm execution time is about 15 minutes it's not convenient to freeze the user browser during for such a time. So, the algorithm will run in its server and, when finished data will be available on SEAS SI. Results provide a list with all, both online and offline, executed algorithms result. The online mode executes the algorithm in real-time and gives the result to the user afterwards. In the offline mode algorithms run in background, without hanging the user computer, and results will be available when processing finishes.

SEAS SI integrates not only the current algorithms but also a case study repository, a new EVs scenario generator and a multi-agent system platform. In the near future, the algorithms will have the ability to run using input data coming from the case study repository and the EV scenario generator, using a seamless approach. The case study repository will receive data from an adapter that allows the conversion of data from the IEEE Intelligent Data Mining and Analysis (IDMA) [11] and Sofia 2 into the SEAS SI standard.

Built for the SEAS project, SEAS SI will also be used in SEAS pilots and demonstrators running in several European countries, such as: France, Finland, Portugal and Turkey. The pilots and demonstrators will use SEAS SI web services to execute algorithms. The data produced in the Pilots and demonstrators will be sent to Sofia 2 platform. These data can also be available in SEAS SI using data adapter to retrieve it from Sofia 2 and storage in the case study repository, where it becomes available for SEAS SI users input to execute SEAS SI algorithms or to be download.

C. Sequential execution of algorithms

The execution of sequences of algorithms can be defined and configured in SEAS SI. The definition of sequences has been designed in order to be flexible and allow the combination of different algorithms, at distinct stages (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. SEAS SI sequence of algorithms concept

The configuration of a sequence of algorithms is composed by the following stages:

- Definition of how many steps are necessary to execute the sequence of algorithms and which algorithms are part of each step, as shown in Figure 4.
- Definition of the connectors between algorithms. A connector between two algorithms is composed by the outputs achieved by the execution of algorithms in the previous step, which type of object matches the type of object expected as input for the algorithms of the following step. The compatibility between objects is assessed by the interface.
- Definition of the necessary inputs to execute the sequence. In this stage it is required that users upload all the inputs that do not derive directly from the output of other algorithms in the sequence. It is also necessary to specify the name and description of the algorithms' sequence. Finally, the user will be able to save the sequence configuration for future use (self or by other partners). After submitting the configurations, if everything is correctly defined, the user will be able to consult the achieved results in the repository page. When the sequence execution is finished, the user is notified by email.

It is also possible to execute pre-configures sequences. The user is able to access the page where all configurations that have been defined and made available by partners are. In order to execute a pre-configured sequence, it is only necessary to download the template of the inputs required for running the sequence; fill it with the desired input data, and submit the execution of the sequence. Later, the user will be able to analyse the achieved results, by consulting the file made available in the repository.

III. ALGORITHMS

At this moment, 10 algorithms from 4 different partners are available in the platform. Some of them are briefly described as follows.

- Net_Profit_F_R_SB** – calculates the annual profitability of frequency regulation service from the main grid for one EV battery used for frequency regulation;
- FreqRegSingleBat** – calculates the profitability of one up/down request from the main grid for one EV battery used for frequency regulation;
- FreqRegScenarioSimul**– simulates the dynamic behavior of an EV battery for frequency regulation. It predicts the

vehicle availability, battery State of Charge (SOC) and calculates the net profit evolution per request

- **IMT-TSP's** - approximation algorithms for EV charging scheduling in SEAS microgrids: optimizing peak and revenue;

From the available algorithms, those used in the work presented in this paper are described as follows:

- **ANN** – Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are inspired on the human brain and their amount of neurons with high interconnectivity. ANNs are constituted by several nodes or neurons, organized in different levels, and interconnected by numeric weights. They resemble to the human brain in two fundamental points: the knowledge being acquired from the surrounding environment, through a learning process; and the network's nodes being interconnected by weights (synaptic weights), used to store the knowledge. Each neuron executes a simple operation, the weighted sum of its input connections, which originates the exit signal that is sent to the other neurons. The network learns by adjusting the connection weights, in order to produce the desired output - the output layer values [12]. Based on a large number of correct examples ANN are able to change their connection weights until they generate outputs that are coincident with the correct values. This way, ANN are able to extract basic rules from data [13].
- **SVM** – In 1936, R. A. Fisher [14] created the first algorithm for pattern recognition. The SVM algorithm is implemented by a generalization of the nonlinear algorithm Generalized Portrait that has been created by Vapnik and Lerner in the sequence of [15]. This was the first running kernel of SVM, only for classification and linear problems. The SVM concept can be tracked to when statistical learning theory was developed further with Vapnik, in 1979. However, the SVM approach in the current form was first introduced with a paper at the COLT conference, in 1992 [16]. The information to use in an SVM must follow the format suggested in (1):

$$[y_1, x_1, \dots, y_n, x_n, R] \quad (1)$$

where each example x_i is a space vector example; y_i has a corresponding value; n is the size of training data. For classification: y_i assumes finite values; in binary classifications: $y_i \in \{+1, -1\}$; in digit recognition : $y_i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 0\}$; and for regression purposes, y_i is a real number ($y_i \in R$). The most applicable kernels for time series forecasting, as in the problem considered in this work, are the

Radial Basis Function (RBF) and the exponential Radial Basis Function (eRBF). These two kernels are specifically directed to regression in time series data.

- **Metalearner** – provides a methodology that considers several different strategies' outputs as basis to build the metalearner's final output, depending on the confidence weight that the system has on each strategy [17]. This means that the better a strategy is performing, the higher its influence on this method's results will be (see Fig.5). This is done through the application of a weighted average of the outputs of all strategies, using their confidence values in each context as weights. The confidence values on each strategy can be the result of a learning process. The generation of this output p is performed through a weighted average, using the reinforcement learning algorithm's confidence values as weights $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_n$ for each strategy's output's $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ contribution to the final metalearner's solution. The procedure is expressed in (2).

$$x_{1,p} p_1 + x_{2,p} p_2 + \dots + x_{n,p} p_n \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5. Metalearner's scaling of the importance of each input [17]

- **MAPE** – The accuracy of the forecast may be evaluated by several error indices, such as the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). In MAPE the average of all percentage errors is computed, producing a measure of relative overall fit (3).

$$MAPE = 100\% \frac{1}{N} \sum_{h=1}^N \left| \frac{F_h - Y_h}{Y_h} \right| \quad (3)$$

IV. CASE STUDY

Some of the SEAS SI algorithms are used to configure a sequence of algorithms in the scope of this work. The ANN is used to forecast time series, and the SVM performs a similar task, using the regression of historic data and training by several alternative kernel functions. These two algorithms are used in parallel, in the first step, to forecast the electricity market prices of MIBEL for one day, namely July 10th, 2016, as available in [7]. MAPE is a well-known forecasting error calculation method; two instances of this algorithm are used in the second step to calculate the forecasting error of the two forecasting methods. Finally, the third step comprehends the application of a metalearner to determine electricity market participation bids. The metalearner provides a methodology that considers several different strategies' outputs as basis to build the metalearner's final output, depending on the confidence weight that the system has on each strategy. This means that the better a strategy is performing, the higher its influence on this method's results will be. This is done through the application of a weighted average of the outputs of all strategies, using their confidence values in each context as weights. In this case, the strategies are the different forecasting methods, and the confidence values are the forecasting errors associated to each forecast.

Figure 6 presents the comparison between the real market price in MIBEL (Portuguese marginal price) in 10th July 2016, and the forecasted prices achieved by the ANN and SVM.

Fig. 6. Market prices: real, and forecasted by ANN and SVM.

From Figure 6 it is possible to see that the forecasting results achieved by using the SVM are closer to the real market prices verified in MIBEL in the considered day. This is reflected in the forecasting error, as shown in Figure 7 (through the comparison of the relative error, in %, between the two considered forecasting approaches).

Fig. 7. Relative error of the forecasts achieved with the ANN and SVM.

From Figure 7 it is possible to confirm that the SVM has, in fact, a much smaller forecasting error than the ANN. This error is directly proportional to the confidence weight that is used by the metalearner when combining the outputs of the two approaches. Therefore, the output of the SVM is considered with more influence over the final metalearner result. This can be seen by Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the electricity market bid price resulting from the metalearner and the real market price

From Figure 8 it is possible to see that the bid price achieved by the metalearner reaches very similar values to those of the real market price. This reflects the metalearner's ability in using the outputs of the forecasting methods appropriately in order to create its own, enhanced output. The SVM results have contributed with a larger weight to the final metalearner output, due to its better forecasting results. On the other hand, the smaller influence of the ANN results have been enough to complement the information gathered from the SVM, and thus help to reach values that are much closer to the real prices.

A simulation using MASCEM is used to assess the results of this algorithms sequence as decision support for electricity market participation. MASCEM is a multi-agent simulator of competitive electricity markets, which uses real data to create realistic simulation scenarios that represent the reality of

different markets. Among the several market operators from which MASCEM has access to real data in order to create representative scenarios, is the Iberian electricity market operator – MIBEL, which is the scenario used for this experiment. A total of 60 days is simulated in MASCEM, considering the day-ahead spot market, and starting on July 1st, 2016. The participation of a subject player is evaluated under three market participation strategies: (i) using the market price forecast provided by the ANN, (ii) using the SVM for market price forecast; and (iii) using the metalearner's results, as result of the presented sequence of algorithms using SEAS SI. Figure 9 shows the total incomes that have been achieved by the subject player in the end of the 60 considered simulated days, when using the three market participation approaches, for a constant hourly sale of 10 MW.

Fig. 9. Incomes achieved by the subject player in the total of the 60 simulated days, using the three market participation approaches.

From Fig. 9 it is possible to see that by using the results from the sequence of algorithms provided by the SEAS SI platform, and benefiting from the more accurate market price forecasting results, the subject player is able to achieve higher incomes than when negotiating in the market using as basis the market price forecasts provided by both the ANN and SVM.

V. CONCLUSIONS

SEAS project has been promoting the intelligent management of smart grids by means of collaborative usage of algorithms and tools, while ensuring confidentiality and interoperability. In this scope, SEAS SI has been developed and presented in this paper, namely its features and architecture. A case study involving several algorithms, written and executed in different programming languages, illustrate SEAS SI advantages to foster new and overwhelming scenarios that cannot be studied using the algorithms independently.

The case study, using different algorithms to reach an enhanced bid price for electricity market negotiations, shows

the advantage of the SEAS SI platform, which provides the means for the sequential execution of different algorithms. The electricity market simulation allows taking further conclusions on the advantages of using such platform, in a scenario of electricity market participation. From these results it can be seen that using sequences of algorithms by means of SEAS SI, better market price forecasting results can be achieved, which leads to better market negotiation results.

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